

Ergativity in Pashto

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Abstract

This study focuses on the ergativity in Pashto. The Minimalist programme of Chomsky is adopted as a framework for analysis. The main area explored in this chapter is the derivation of Pashto's ergative structures. The results show that in Pashto ergativity is assigned in both past tense and perfect aspect. Moreover, volitionality also plays a significant role in determining the ergative of subject in Pashto. Ergative case was found assigned to subject in past tense and perfect aspect if and only if the action denoted was volitional.

Introduction

Ergativity

There are three possible core arguments of the verb, namely subject of the intransitive Verb (S), subject with agent role (A) and object of the transitive Verb (O). A possible way to distinguish these arguments would be to have different cases for each of them. Having different cases for the S, A and O is not so common among the languages of the world. A very common case system is the one in which two cases exist, namely, case of subject of both transitive and intransitive verbs and case of the object of transitive verb. This kind of system is called Nominative/Accusative which exists in most of the European family of languages (Tallerman 2005:161). The same is true for English which comes from European family of languages. Examples in (1) illustrates nominative/accusative pattern in English.

1.
 - a. We (S) laugh.
 - b. We (A) hit her (O).
 - c. She (S) laughs.
 - d. she (A) is hit by us (O).

In (1a) *we* is the subject of an intransitive verb *laugh*, while in (1b) *we* is the subject of a transitive verb *eat* but the case of both the subjects, namely, the subject of the transitive verb and the subject of the intransitive is the same. However, the case of the object of the transitive verb *her* in (1b) is different from the case of the subject of an intransitive verb in (1c) and that of the case of the subject of transitive verb in (1d).

The other system of case marking is the one which marks A differently from the subject of the intransitive Verb (S) and object of the transitive Verb (O). This kind of system of case marking is known as ergative/ absolutive system of case marking. The case of agent subject, the subject of the transitive verb is ergative while absolutive is the case of unagentive subject. The subject, in (2) shows the two systems of case marking.

2.

Accusative System	
A.S	O
Nominative	Accusative

Ergative System	
A	S.O
Ergative	Absolutive

Accusative system is common in European languages like English, Latin, German etc, while ergative system is in vogue in Australian languages like lezgein and Basque. Ergative system is not found in European languages (Roman, Germanic, Celtic, Greek etc). It is very rare in Africa. However, in Australian languages, ergativity is very common. As for as South Asian languages are concerned, they display split ergativity. Indo-Aryan family of languages is famous for split ergativity. Besides, Indo-Iranian family of languages also display split ergativity. Pashto is belongs to Indo-Iranian family of languages which is the focus of this study.

4.1.1. Split System.

All the languages cannot be classified either accusative or ergative. There are some languages which show a system which combine the properties of both ergative and accusative languages. Such kinds of languages are called split ergative languages. There are a number of factors that determine the split on ergativity; firstly, the semantic property of NPs; secondly, the tense or aspect of the verb; and, finally the type of clause; main or embedded.

In Dyirbal, an Australian language split is triggered by the property of NPs. Full NPs and third person pronoun take up ergative case. (Tallerman.2005:165) Pitta-Pitta, an another Australian language, displays split on tense of the verb; in non-future tense, the subject have ergative case while in future tense, it has nominative case.

In Gojri, on the other hand, agentive subject carries ergativity maker *-ne* in simple past tense and perfective aspects (Sharma 1982). Moreover, in Gojri, the ergative maker *-ne* cannot co-occur with clause that contains a verb in habitual and progressive aspect (Akhtar & Bukhari 2007), Other Indo-Aryan languages such as Punjabi (Akhtar 2000), Urdu (Butt 1995) and Hindi (Mahajan 1989) display the same pattern. Examples in (3) illustrates split on ergativity in Dyirbal and some Ando-Aryan languages.

3.

- | | | | | |
|----|---|--|-----------------------|--------------------------------|
| a. | Nguma
Father-Abs
Mother (A) | yabu-nggu
mother-Erg
saw father (O). | buran
saw | |
| | | | | (Dyirbal. Tallerman 2005) |
| b. | Kajal-ne
Kajal-ERG
Kajal has read | Xat
letter-NOM
the book. | likhyo
write PF be | e
PRES-3.s |
| | | | | (Gojri. Akhtar & Bukhari 2007) |
| c. | DaakTar-ne
Doctor-ERG
The doctor examined | mariiz-nuñ
patient-ACC
the patient. | vekhi-aa
see-PST | |
| | | | | (Punjabi. Akhtar 2000) |
| d. | Ram-ne
Ram-ERG
Ram had eaten | rotti
bread
bread. | khaayii
eat-PERF-F | thii
be-past-f |
| | | | | (Hindi. Mahajan 1989) |

In every illustration given in (3) one of the arguments of the verb is ergative case. In case of Dyirbal as in (3a) the subject *yabu* carries *nggu* as an ergative case marker. In case of Gojri as in (3b) *-ne* marks the subject Kajal as ergative. Panjabi and Hindi use the same *-ne* to mark an of the verb as ergative as *-ne* marks DaaKtar and Ram ergative in (3c) and (3d) respectively.

4.1.2. Morphological Ergativity in Pashto

Pashto is a split ergative language where ergativity is both structural and morphological. Data in (4) show that subject of intransitive verb (S) and subject of transitive verb (A), regardless of having different forms, behave similarly under identical syntactic conditions.

4.2. Type of Clause and Ergativity

Type of clause makes no difference to the ergative pattern of a clause. The same ergative pattern is followed both in matrix and embedded clause. As the subject of the transitive clause is assigned ergative case in past tense (both perfect and imperfect past) and perfect aspect in non past tenses in the main clause, so does happen in the embedded clause. Regardless of the semantic properties of the verb in the matrix clause, the agentive subject of the embedded clause is assigned ergative case in past and perfect aspects in non past tenses. Data in (8) show that the type of clause makes no difference to the ergative pattern inside the clause. Once the conditions for ergative case are met, no matter what type of clause it is, ergative case is assigned to its subject.

4.

- | | | | | | | | |
|----|---------------------------|--------------------|-----------------|--------------------------------|--|------------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| a. | Hagha
He (NOM) | wai
say | chi
cp | hagha
he (NOM) | ba
fut | kitab
book (NOM) | wakhli
buy (3.s) |
| | | | | | | | He says that he will buy a book. |
| b. | <i>Ma wi</i>
I (ERG) | <i>chi</i>
said | <i>za</i>
CP | <i>ba cherg</i>
I (NOM) fut | <i>pokh</i>
chicken (NOM) | <i>krham</i>
cook | do (1.s Pres) |
| | | | | | | | I said that I will cook the chicken. |
| c. | <i>Za waim</i>
I (NOM) | <i>chi</i>
say | <i>ma</i>
CP | <i>cherg</i>
I (ERG) | <i>pokh kare</i>
chicken (s.m) cook | <i>de</i>
do (s.m) be(s.m Pres) | |
| | | | | | | | I say that I have cooked the chicken. |

In (8b) the subject of matrix clause is in ergative case while the subject of the embedded clause is in nominative case, in view of the fact that matrix clause is in past tense and the embedded clause in present tense. Similarly, the subject of the matrix clause in (8c) is in nominative case while the subject of the embedded clause is in ergative case in view of the fact that Asp head carries [-IMPF]₁ features and subject is assigned agent theta role which require that the subject of the clause be in ergative case.

4.3. Ergativity in Pashto

Pashto is a split ergative language like some other Indo-Iranian languages. The same phenomenon can be seen in Indo-Aryan languages like Hindi, Urdu, Punjabi, Gojri etc. Split in Indo-Aryan languages is subject to the semantic properties of the subject NP₁; and aspect, tense and mood of the clause. In Gojri, ergative case marker *-né* appears on agent subject in past tense and perfective aspects and same is the case with Hindi, Urdu, Punjabi etc. In Pashto, the case is quite similar to that of Indo-Aryan languages, since here ergative case is assigned to agent subject in perfect aspects in all the tenses. However, there is an exception that in Pashto, in addition to perfect aspect, ergative case is assigned to agentive subject in past tense too.

In Pashto, there exist only two aspects namely perfect and imperfect while in Indo-Aryan languages there are three aspects including Habitual, Progressive and Perfect. Imperfect aspect in Pashto encompasses both habitual and progressive which are treated separately in Indo-Aryan languages. Consequently, in Pashto ergative case is assigned in past progressive too in addition to past simple and perfect while in Indo-Aryan languages ergative case is not assigned in progressive aspect despite of the fact that the other requirements such as agentive role and volitionality of action are fulfilled.

Examples in (09) illustrates that in Pashto ergative case is assigned to subject in past progressive in addition to past simple and perfect tense.

1. The semantic properties of a subject NP mean that whether the subject agent or experiencer.

5.

- a. Ma xér wowaxo
I (ERG) donkey (NOM) see PST S.M
I beat donkey.
- b. Ma xér waxo
I (ERG) donkey (NOM) see PST S.M
I was beating the donkey.
- c. Ma rotai xwara
I (ERG) meal (NOM) eat. PST S.M
I was eating the meal.
- d. Ma rotai xwarali da
I (ERG) meal (NOM) eat PF be. S.F.Pres
I have eaten the meal.
- e. Ma ba kor aghast wi.
I (ERG) FUT house buy be PST
I will have bought the house.
- f. Ma ba kor aghasto
I (ERG) FUT house buy PST
I would have been buying a house.
- g. Ma kor aghaste wo
I (ERG) house buy PF be.PST
I had bought the house.

Illustrations in (09) shows that in Pashto agentive subject has ergative case in past tense and perfect aspect in non past tense. Another important aspect of ergativity in Pashto is that all the subjects bearing ergative case must have agent theta role which entails that the action performed by subject is volitional. The same is true about Indo-Aryan languages (Bukhari & Akhtar. 2008) (Akhtar & Bukhari 2007) Butt (1995). Examples in (10) illustrations a situation in which the subject does not carry agent theta role and thus ergative case is not assigned to it.

6.

- a. Zama salma xwaxa da
 I (DAT) Salma (NOM) like PF be (Pres)
 I like salma/ I love salma.

In its place, if ergative case is assigned to the subject in (10), the sentence becomes ungrammatical. Consider the following:

7.

- a. *ma salma xwaxa da
 I (DAT) Salma (NOM) like PF be (Pres)
 I like salma/ I love salma.

In Pashto, ergativity is observed in past tense and perfect aspects. In past tense in both perfect and imperfect aspect exhibit ergativity while in non past tenses it is restricted to perfect aspects. (11) Demonstrates that ergative case assignment to subject in present imperfect results in ungrammaticality. However, nominative subject is fine at that position. Contrastively, in present perfect ergative case is fine whereas nominative case on subject results in ill-formedness. Consider the following:

8.

- a. Za kitab goram
 I (NOM) book (ACC) read 1.s Pres
 I read a book/ I am reading a book.
- b. *Ma kitab axlam
 I (NOM) book (ACC) buy 1.s Pres
 I buy a book/ I am buying a book.
- c. Ma kitab aghaste de
 I (ERG) book (NOM) buy PF be 3.s Pres.
 I have bought a book.
- d. *Za kitab katale de
 I (ERG) book (NOM) read PF be 3.s Pres.
 I have read a book.

In most of the Indo-Aryan languages like Urdu (Butt,1995,1997), Punjabi (Akhtar,2000) and Gojri (Bukhari & Akhtar.2008) the action performed by ergative subject is volitional. Wali (2005) argues that ergativity in Maharati is conditioned by subjunctive mood. He further assumes that in Maharati ergative case is assigned to the subject of those sentences which denote obligation and necessity. In Pashto too, where ergative case is assigned to the subject, volitionality is evident in the action performed by the agent subject as shown in (13):

9.

- a. Ma gellax mat kare de
 I (ERG) glass (NOM) break do PF be s.m Pres
 I have broken the glass. **(Volitional act)**
- b. Zama na gellax mat sho
 I (GEN) glass (NOM) break PF be s.m PST
 I have broken the glass
(Non volitional action)
- c. Ma ghwa xarsa krha.
 I (ERG) cow (NOM) sell do s.f PST
 I sold the cow.
(Volitional action)
- d. Zama na ghwa wraka shwa.
 I (GEN) cow (NOM) lose PF be s.f Pres
 I have lost a cow.
(Non Volitional Action)
- e. Ma korsai mata krhi da
 I (ERG) chair (NOM) break do PF be.s.f.Pres
 I have broken the chair.
(Volitional Action)
- f. Da hagma na korsai mata shwa

He (GEN) chair (NOM) break be.s.f.Pres
 He broke the chair.

(Non Volitional Action)

The action of the subject in (13f as in 13b and d) is non volitional because of the fact that the subject is not agent in those constructions. The action is not intentional thus the case of the subject is not ergative even though the structural requirements for ergativity such as tense and aspect are fulfilled. Thus it is proved that the action performed by an ergative subject is always volitional. Non-volitional action on the part of the subject requires it to be genitive case, as it happens in (13b, d and f). Consequently, a very close association between volitionality and ergativity is evident. However, there are some constructions which behave quite uniquely with respect to ergativity and transitivity of verb.

Consider the following:

10.

- a. Ma wakhandal
 I (ERG) laugh. PL. PST
 I laughed
- b. Ma wajaral
 I (ERG) weep.PL. PST
 I wept.

The action performed by subject in (14a) is not volitional, neither is the verb a transitive one. However, despite of all this, ergative case is assigned to the subject. Moreover, the nominative subject causes ungrammaticality as it happen in (15a-b)

11.

- a. *Za wakhandal
 I (NOM) laugh. PL. PST
 I laughed.
- b. *Za wajaral
 I (NOM) weep.PL. PST
 I wept.

In the following section, ergativity in Pashto is discussed in detail, with special focus on the condition under which subject in a clause is assigned ergative case. The conditions include tense, aspect, the thematic properties of Subject NP and the thematic properties of verb.

4.3.1. Pashto Ergative case Inherent or Structural?

Bobaljik (1993) claims that ergativity in south Asian languages is structural. Ergative case is structural case in these languages due to the fact that it is based on a particular structure of the clause; perfect aspect, past tense etc. However, it is equally liable to argue that ergative case in South Asian languages including, Hindi, Urdu, Panjabi, Gojri etc is inherent due to the fact that only agent subject bears ergative case marker. (Bukhari & Akhtar 2008) (Akhtar & Bukhari 2007)

Subject with experiencer role can never bear ergative case as in (16). In Gojri, experiencer subjects are marked with -nā which is a dative and accusative case marker. Similarly, in Pashto too, Genitive case, a case other than ergative, is assigned to experiencer subject.

12.

- a. Zama yakhni washwa
 I (GEN) cold be PST
 I felt cold.
- b. *Ma yakhni washwa
 I (ERG) cold be PST
 I felt cold.
- c. Zama pa ser dard wo.
 I (GEN) head (DAT) pain be PST
 I was feeling headache.
- d. Pa ma taba raghali wa.

I (DAT) fever come FPbe s.f Pres
I was suffering from fever.

In Pashto, ergative case is not visible in form of a clitic unlike Gojri and other Indo-Aryan languages where ergative case has a special marker. In Urdu, *-na* is ergative case marker. In Pashto, the case is very different here in case of noun (both common and proper) no change is made to the form of the noun. Agreement pattern inside the clause determine the case of the subject. If the verb agrees with subject, the latter is in nominative case. While in case the verb agrees with object, the subject is in ergative case. However, in case of pronouns, the base form is changed. The following table illustrates the ergative and nominative pronouns in Pashto.

13.

Nominative		Ergative
First person singular	Za	Ma
First person plural	mong	Mong or monga
Second person singular	Tê	Taa
Second person plural	Taso	taso
Third person singular Masc	Hagha	haghê
FEM	Hagha	haghi
Third person plural	haghoi	haghoi

From the above table, it is clear that the ergative form of first person singular pronoun is *ma* (I) while in the nominative form of *ma* (I) is *za* (I). The ergative form of second person singular pronoun is *taa* (you) while its nominative form is *tê* (you). The ergative and nominative form of second person plural is the same. The ergative form of third person singular masculine is *haghê* while its nominative form is *hagha* while its singular ergative feminine is *haghi* with a slight difference in the last vowel. The ergative and nominative form of third person plural is the same.

As it is true for Gojri, in Pashto too, inanimate subject NP cannot be assigned ergative case. This entails that ergativity in Pashto is an inherent case. Illustrations in (18) confirm that an inanimate subject NP cannot be assigned ergative case.

14.

- a. *Kursai rotai waxwara
Chair (ERG)meal (NOM) eat.sg.F. PST
Chair eats the meal.
- b. *Laptop woba skali di
Laptop (ERG) water (NOM) drink FPbe.sg.F.Pres
Laptop has drunk water.

The examples in (18) illustrate that ergativity is closely associated with the agent role of the subject to which the case is assigned. Kursi 'chair' is an inanimate entity which cannot perform the action of eating. Similarly, laptop is an inanimate object which cannot be involved in a volitional action. Thus, they cannot be marked with an ergative case, despite the fact that all other requirements of ergative case namely, past tense or perfect aspect, are satisfied. The sole cause of ungrammaticality of constructions in (18) is that the subject is an inanimate entity.

Thus it is concluded that in Pashto, like Gojri and other Indo-Aryan languages, ergative case is both structural and inherent. Structural in the sense that subject bears ergative case only when the structural requirements for ergative case such as past tense and/or perfect aspect are met. The thematic requirement is to have subject with agent theta role. Experiencer subject cannot be assigned ergative case. Moreover, like Gojri, in Pashto too ergative case is not allowed on an inanimate subject NP.

4.3.2. Ergative Case Assignment in Pashto

Uptil now, it has been established that in Pashto ergative case is both inherent and structural. The thematic requirement of ergativity is to have subject with agent theta role. The subject NP enters the derivation with an uninterpretable and unvalued features that need to be valued and deleted in the course of time. For two reasons these uninterpretable features are checked and valued; firstly, at PF, an NP cannot be pronounced unless the case that it bears is valued and secondly, the deletion of the uninterpretable features at LF is possible only when the case features are valued. This phenomenon of case checking is in line with the claim of Chomsky (1995) and Nunes (1995: 231), who argue that uninterpretable features are illegitimate, at LF.

Following Chomsky (1995, 2000, 2001), it is assumed that T assigns nominative case to the closest NP it C-commands and which does not already have a case value. In nominative-accusative constructions subject is the closest available NP is in consequence ready for nominative case assignment. On the other hand, little *v* assigns agent theta role to the subject and accusative case to the object in transitive constructions. Conditions on ergativity in Pashto can be generalized as in (19).

15.

- a. Ergative case is assigned to subject NP that bears agent theta role and that the Asp head carries [-IMPF], or otherwise T head is marked for [+PST].
- b. However, if Asp is marked [+IMPF] ergative case is still assigned when T head is marked for past tense.

1. the semantic property of subject that is relevant here is that ergative it must carry agent theta role
Bukhari & Akhtar (2008) postulates the following generalization about ergativity in Gojri.

16.

- a. The ergative case is assigned to a subject when (a) the Asp head is marked for [-IMPf] and (b) *v* assigns agent theta role to the subject NP.

The given generalization about ergativity in Pashto entails that ergativity in Pashto is relevant to tense, aspect and the semantic property of the subject NP₁. The rest of the possible conditions like type of clause and mood are irrelevant in this regard.

The aspectual system of Pashto is not rich like that of Indo-Aryan languages. There are only two aspects in Pashto; namely, perfect and imperfect. The aspect head realizes it aspect as [-IMPf] and imperfect as [+IMP]. So it is very convenient to capture both the features as binary features [+IMPf] as Bukhari & Akhtar (2008) proposes for Gojri. When the aspect head has the value [-IMPf], the subject NP in the spec/vP is assigned ergative case. So perfect aspect is realized as [-IMPf], while imperfect aspect is realized as [+IMPf]. In this way, ergative case is assigned to subject in perfect aspect. However, if the aspect head carries [+IMPf] features and T head carries [PST], the subject is assigned ergative case regardless of the features that the Asp head carries. In case the T head carries [Pres], then the aspect head needs to be in [-IMPf], otherwise ergative case is not assigned. Thus, it implies that ergative case is assigned in both in past perfect and imperfect constructions. As it happens in Gojri and Maharati, in Pashto aspect morphology is always visible as a suffix on verb. Consider the following.

17.

- a. Kaloo-ne ka kepyo
Kaloo (ERG) grass (NOM) cut PST
Kaloo cuts the grass

Gojri. (Bukhari.2008)
- b. Ma wakha rebali di.
I (ERG) grass (NOM) cut PF be.1.sg.M.Pres
I have cut the grass.

From the above discussion it is concluded that in Pashto, ergative case is based on agentivity, aspect and tense. In Gojri, ergativity is based on agentivity and aspect only. Tense plays no role in this regard. Bukhari & Akhtar (2000) argue that past tense always combines with perfect aspect but in Pashto we cannot combine past imperfect with perfect since in Pashto imperfect aspect includes both progressive and habitual which are treated separately in Gojri. In Gojri, ergative case is assigned only in past habitual, not in past progressive, in addition to perfect aspect in past and non past tenses. However, in Pashto, ergative case is assigned in both habitual and progressive aspects in past tense in addition to perfect aspect aspects in past and non past tense. Consider the following examples.

18.

- a. Ma rotai xwarhali.
I (ERG) meal (NOM) eat. 3.s.f PST
I was eating the meal
- b. Ma rotai wexwarha.
I (ERG) meal (NOM) eat. 3.s.f PST
I ate the meal.

c.	Ma	rotai	xwarhali	wa.
	I (ERG)	meal (NOM)	eat.PF	be. 3. S.f PST
	I had eaten the meal.			

The following structure illustrates ergative case assignment in Pashto.

19.

First of all, the verb merges to the object, forming VP then the v merges with vP, to form v' which merges with its specifier subject DP to form vP. Here at this stage, the little v assigns agent theta role to the subject which is one of the requirements for the subject DP in the spec/v position before getting marked for ergative case. After this, vP merges with Asp to form AspP. At this point in the process of derivation, if the Asp head carries [-IMPF] features then ergative case is assigned to the subject hence the requirements for ergative case are met. Since in the above given structure Asp head bears [-IMPF] features, the subject is assigned ergative case. However, if the Asp head bears [+IMPF] feature, then the features of the T head to be checked. If the latter is marked for past tense [+PST] then ergative case is assigned to the subject regardless of the features of Asp head, since in Pashto ergative case is assigned to agent subject in past tense; in all aspects. Review the following structure.

20.

wo and *de* are the realization of tense; past and present tense respectively. It is, therefore liable to argue that in Pashto tense is realized with clitics as it happens in English. In Pashto –wo is an auxiliary which is positioned at

the end of the clause as in (25c). However, in progressive aspect it becomes a part of the adjective part of the verb as in (25b) and thus it is no more treated as an auxiliary. The habitual aspect in past tense is shown with the tense marker attached to the verb as a prefix as in (25).

21.

- a. Ma poster walagawalo
I (ERG) poster (NOM) paste (Hab)
I pasted the poster.
- b. Ma poster lagawal(w)o
I (ERG) poster (NOM) paste (Prog)
I pasted the poster.
- c. Ma poster lagawale wo
I (ERG) poster (NOM) paste PF be. sg.M.PST
I had pasted the poster.

4.4. Derivation of Clause in Pashto

This section focuses on case, agreement and derivation of Pashto clause along with different patterns of case marking and their effect on verbal agreement. Only a caseless NP is assigned Nominative case by T. In this regard, Bukhari & Akhtar (2008) maintain that nominative case has a special relation to agreement in many south Asian languages. Accusative is commonly realized by an overt case marking in comparison to nominative which is usually a base as it does not exhibit any case marking.

Following Chomsky, it is assumed that structural case is assigned to an NP by functional head such as T while lexical case is assigned to an NP by little v. Accusative case is assigned to an object NP by little v while ergative case is assigned by Asp head when the structural and lexical requirements for its assignment are fulfilled.

The conditions on ergative case in Pashto are the same as those for Gojri Bukhari & Akhtar (2008) except for tense which also plays a major role in this regard. In case the T head carries [+PST] features, ergative case is assigned regardless of the features that the Asp head carries. However, if the T head carries [-PST] features then in order for the subject to be assigned ergative, the Asp head must be marked with [-IMPF] features.

The rules of case and agreement of Pashto are as follows.

22.

- a. Nominative case is assigned to an NP that values the phi-features of T, regardless of the grammatical function of the latter; it may be the subject or the object.
- b. Following the economy principle, the verb agrees with the highest available nominative NP₁
- c. If a clause does not have nominative NP at subject position which is the highest position in the clause then the verb agrees with nominative NP at object position. In case of double objects, the verb agrees with direct object which is always nominative case in Pashto.
- d. Accusative case is assigned to an object by little v and is covertly checked if the clause take single object (Chomsky.1995)
- e. If the subject NP is assigned experiencer role instead, Genitive case is assigned to it concurrently.
- f. If the little v assigns agent theta role to its external argument and the Asp head carries [-IMP] features then the subject NP is valued for ergative case.
- g. However, if the T head is marked with [+PST] features then the case of subject is valued as ergative regardless of the features of Asp head.

Conclusion

The study concludes that in Pashto ergativity is assigned in both past tense and perfect aspect. Moreover, volitionality also plays a significant role in determining the ergative of subject in Pashto. Ergative case was found assigned to subject in past tense and perfect aspect iff the action denoted was volitional. Nominative case is assigned to an NP that values the phi-features of T, regardless of the grammatical function of the latter; it may be the subject or the object. If a clause does not have nominative NP at subject position which is the highest position in the clause then the verb agrees with nominative NP at object position. In case of double objects, the verb agrees with direct object which is always nominative case in Pashto. Accusative case is assigned to an object by little v and is covertly checked if the clause take single object (Chomsky.1995) If the subject NP is assigned experiencer role instead, Genitive case is assigned to it concurrently. If the little v assigns agent theta role to its external argument and the Asp head carries [-IMP] features then the subject NP is valued for ergative

case. However, if the T head is marked with [+PST] features then the case of subject is valued as ergative regardless of the features of Asp head.

References

- Adger, D. 2001. *Core Syntax: A minimalist approach*. New York: Oxford UP
- Akhtar, R.N (2000). *Aspectual Complex Predicates in Punjabi*. Ph.d thesis, University of Essex, Colchester
- Aldridge, Edith. 2008. *Phase-based Account of Extraction in Indonesian*. *Lingua* 118.10:1440-1469.
- Bobaljik, J. D and P. Branigan. (2003). *Eccentric Agreement and Multiple Case Checking*. In J.A. Massam, D & Ndayiragije, k. (eds), *ergativity: emerging issues*.
- Bobaljik, J. D. (1993), *Ergativity and Ergative Unergatives*. In Philips, C(ed), *Papers on Case and Agreement II, MIT Working Papers in Linguistics* 19: 45-88
- Bobaljik, J. D. (2004) *Long Distance Agreement in Hindi: Some Theoretical Implications*. *Studia linguistica* 58:23-36.
- Bukhari, N.H (2008) *The Clause Structure Of Gojri In Minimalist Program: Kashmir journal of language research. Vol.11 No.1* Department of English University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan
- Bukhari, N.H, Akhtar, R. N (2007) *Ergativity In Gojri: Kashmir journal of language research. Vol.10 No.1* Department of English University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan
- Butt, M. (1997). *Complex Predicates in Urdu*, In Alsina, A., J. Bresnan and P. Sells (eds), *Complex Predicates*. Stanford: CSLI Publications.
- Butt, M. 1995. *The structure of complex predicates in Urdu*. Stanford: CSLI Publications.
Center for Applied Linguistics
- Chomsky, N (1993) *A Minimalist Programme for Linguistic Theory*. In Keyser, K.H.A.S.J. (ed.) *The View from Building 20: Essays in Linguistics in Honour of Sylvain Bromberger*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Chomsky, N (1995). *The Minimalist Program*. Cambridge MA: MIT press.
- Chomsky, N (1998) *Derivation by Phase*. MIT occasional papers in linguistics 18: Cambridge, MA: MIT PRESS .
- Chomsky, N (2001) *Derivation by Phase*. In Kentowicz, M. (ed.) *Ken Hale. A life in language*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. (1-52)
- Chomsky, N (2005) *On Phases*. MS, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Chomsky, N. & H. Lasnik (1993). *The theory of principal and parameters*. In Jacobs, J, A. V Stechow, W. Sternefeld & T Vennemann (eds) *Syntax: An international handbook of contemporary research*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter. 506-69
- Chomsky, N. (2000) *Minimalist Inquiries: the framework*. En: *Step by Step: Essays on Minimalist Syntax in Honor of Howard Lasnik*, eds. Roger Martin, David Michaels and Juan Uriagereka, Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
- Davison, A (2003). *Word Order, Parameters and the COMP Projection*. Paper presented at the international conference on the south Asian linguistics, University of Hyderabad, India.
- Dixon, R. (1994). *Ergativity*. Cambridge Studies in Linguistics 69. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Keppel, M.G, Khan, Q.A.G & Khan S. A.Q. (1922) *Manual of Pashto*. Crosby Lockwood and Son. LONDON.
- Kumar, R. (2006). *Negation and Licencing og Negative Polarity Items in Hindi syntax*. New York: Oxford University Press. 50-51
- Mahajan, A. (1989) *Agreement and Agreement Phrases*. MIT Working Papers in linguistics 10. 217-252
- Mahajan, A. (1997). *Argument Structure in Hindi*. Standard: CSLI publications.
- Musabhiien, M. (2008) *A Phase-based Analysis of Arabic Structural Case: Kashmir journal of language research. Vol.11 No.1* Department of English University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan
- Nunes, J. (1995). *The copy theory of movement and linearization of chains in the minimalist Program*, Ph.d thesis, University of Maryland, College Park
- Robert, T (2000). *A doctoral dissertation on Clitics and Agreement*, MS, Cambridge, MA MIT
- Sharma, J.C. (1983) *Gojri Grammar*. Maysore: Central Institute of Indian Languages.
- Tallerman, M. (2005). *Understanding Syntax* (2nd ed) Hodder Arnold. London
- Tegey, H, and Barbara R. 1996. *Pashto reference grammar*. Washington, D.C.:
- Woolford, E (1997). *Four-Way Case System: Ergative, Nominative, Objective and Accusative*. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 18.181-227
- Yayudu, A. (2007) *Issues in the syntax of Maharathi: A minimalist Approach*. PhD thesis, Durham University.

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